
RELATIONS AND PROSPECTS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN WITH INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Elmurodov Jonibek Akbar o'g'li

Sharof Rashedov nomidagi Samarqand Davlat Universiteti magistranti

Abstract.

This article talks about the role of the Republic of Kazakhstan in international relations. It talks about Kazakhstan's relationship with international organizations.

Keywords.

social relations, economic cooperation, foreign policy, international relations,

The foreign policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan is distinguished by its activity, striving for balance, pragmatism, attempts to conduct constructive dialogue and orientation to multilateral cooperation. Based on its historical, geopolitical and economic factors, our country has conducted its foreign policy in the international arena for many centuries based on the principles of international cooperation, reconciliation with neighboring countries and respect for their regional unity. The fact that Kazakhstan is ready to establish equal and mutually beneficial relations with other countries is evidenced by the large number of foreign countries that have established diplomatic relations today. Since gaining independence in 1991, our republic has established diplomatic relations with 130 countries of the world. For many reasons, Central Asia and the Kazakhstan region are now receiving special attention in world politics. Due to the rapid pace of development, Kazakhstan is attracting great interest from multinational corporations and other countries. It can be seen that Kazakhstan is the most geographically diverse country in Central Asia, besides, our country is the leader in the region in terms of the rate of economic development. At the same time, it should be taken into account that the country has many opportunities for future development.

Today, the priorities of Kazakhstan's foreign policy are primarily Russia, China, the USA and the European Union. It is aimed at establishing equal relations with neighboring countries in the Central Asian region and the Islamic world. In this regard, in 2006-2007, bilateral relations with the mentioned countries and regions have developed significantly. Following the official visits of the state leadership to Washington, Moscow, Brussels, London, Beijing, Cairo, Tehran,

Tashkent, Bishkek and many other countries' capitals, a number of important documents concerning the interests of the country were signed. bear witness to it. Thus, our country is among the leading countries of the world and neighboring CIS countries. It can be said that the strategic partnership between the countries has reached a new level.

COOPERATION WITH CENTRAL ASIAN STATES

At the moment, Kazakhstan's cooperation with the neighboring Central Asian countries, which has established kinship, cultural, political and economic ties for many centuries, is developing at a particularly fast pace. Kazakhstan is not only the largest country in the region, but is interested in establishing close relations with neighboring countries in the region due to its significantly developed economy. Today's rapid development of our country is closely related to relations with these republics. That is why Kazakhstan is promoting the idea of creating the Central Asian Union.

Apart from Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan are members of the Union. Such countries may also change. In 2006-2007, during the visits of the presidents of the Central Asian countries to Astana and the official visits of the leadership of Kazakhstan to the countries of the region, important bilateral agreements were adopted, which are the basis for the development of interstate cooperation. , political-economic and socio-cultural relations. These documents strengthen Kazakhstan's relations with neighboring countries and give a significant impetus to the implementation of the idea of the Central Asian Union.

COOPERATION WITH THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

One of the main directions of Kazakhstan's foreign policy is relations with Russia. Our country has close relations with this country for many years. The length of the common state border is 7591 km. The interstate commonwealth is developing due to close relations between the presidents and peoples of the two countries. Relations between Kazakhstan and Russia are established in the fields of fuel and energy complex, transport and communication, military equipment and defense industry. The entire range of relations between Kazakhstan and Russia is regulated by numerous bilateral documents and agreements. In addition to mutual relations, the two countries actively cooperate in the framework of many regional organizations of a military, political and economic nature in the region. This word was associated with the Commonwealth of Independent States, the Eurasian Economic Community, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and the Collective Security Treaty Organization. In 2012, Kazakhstan and Russia will celebrate the 20th anniversary of the establishment of diplomatic relations.

Cooperation with the People's Republic of China

The relations of our country with other neighboring countries are rapidly developing. This is the People's Republic of China. The volume of trade between the two countries is increasing every year, many projects are being implemented in the fields of economic, cultural and humanitarian cooperation. Relations between the leaders of the two countries are strengthening due to continuous communication.

COOPERATION WITH THE USA

In addition, Kazakhstan's relations with the United States of America are getting stronger every year. The official visit of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N. Nazarbayev to the USA in 2006 was an important event that served the development and strengthening of Kazakh-American relations. During the visit, the participation of American companies in the process of ensuring security in constructive negotiations between the two countries, the fight against terrorism, the development of communications in the energy sector, and the development of high-tech, innovative industry in the Republic of Kazakhstan were discussed.

Cooperation with Muslim countries If we dwell on the deepening of Kazakhstan's relations with the Islamic world, it can be noted that in 2006-2007, the momentum of these relations was observed. In 2007, the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, N. Nazarbayev, visited Egypt, Jordan, Qatar, Syria, and the United Arab Emirates. Return with an official visit. President of Egypt H. Mubarak and King Abdullah II of Jordan arrived in Kazakhstan. All this is evidence that the relations between our country and the Islamic and Arab world have reached a new level. For example, the official visit of the head of our state to the Syrian Arab Republic in November 2007 was an important event. This was the first visit of the head of our country to the Syrian state, which has great influence in the Arab and Muslim world. Great scholars directly related to the history of Kazakhstan are buried on the territory of this country. They are the great scientist and pedagogue Abu Nasir Farabi, who came from the Kazakh steppe and is buried today in Damascus, and the legendary general and ruler Sultan Baybaris. It is not for nothing that they are allocating funds for the construction and repair of Sultan Beybaris mausoleum. Today, our republic promotes the idea of developing the "West-Muslim world" dialogue between the leading countries of the West and the Islamic world, which is relevant on a global scale, and is promoting this idea. foreign ministers. Kazakhstan is advancing this idea based on its international experience of uniting world religions and creating an opportunity for interreligious dialogue. An example of this is the congress of leaders of world and traditional

religions, which was held three times in our country in 2003, 2006 and 2009 and was highly evaluated at the international level. Speaking at the 62nd session of the UN General Assembly, the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N.A. Nazarbayev suggested holding the upcoming congress within the framework of the UN.

COOPERATION WITH INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Forming a positive image of our country in the international community and gaining an international status became possible thanks to the far-sighted decisions of the republic's leadership in conducting foreign policy. From this point of view, it is possible to emphasize the problems of non-proliferation of nuclear weapons, resistance to religious extremism, establishment of tolerant relations between world religions. Based on this, our country had the opportunity to enter the international arena on its own initiative in the interests of regional and global security. As an example, Kazakhstan's Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe can be mentioned. It can be noted that in 2003, as the leader of the countries of the former Soviet space, he put forward his candidacy for the chairmanship of the OSCE. In recent years, Kazakhstan has shown thoroughness and diligence in realizing this goal. Our country's presidential candidate was supported by many countries that appreciated Kazakhstan's achievements in the field of international security. One of the reasons why Kazakhstan is a candidate for the chairmanship of the OSCE is to make the organization a strong and effective organization that can cope with the various and increasing threats that are emerging in its council. The result of Kazakhstan's desire to chair the OSCE was the decision adopted by the Council of Foreign Ministers of the OSCE member states held in Madrid in November 2007. As a result of this decision, Kazakhstan became the chairman of the OSCE in 2010. The decision of the Madrid Foundation is the only evidence that the international community has recognized the importance of Kazakhstan's achievements as an independent country over the past 18 years. At the same time, it is worth noting that Kazakhstan, as the chairman of this international organization, can make a number of proposals to solve current problems aimed at ensuring international security. Kazakhstan's solid experience in providing security is attracting great interest at the international level, and it is sure to give a positive impetus to the development of the OSCE. Because the chairmanship of the OSCE is an opportunity for Kazakhstan's integration into the European security regional system, to continue equal dialogue with the main members of the organization on the solution of common European current issues. Achievements of Kazakh diplomacy President of the Republic of Kazakhstan N.A. Nazarbayev's Council on Mutual Cooperation

and Trust Measures in Asia This is the implementation of the idea of the meeting. The head of Kazakhstan expressed this opinion in October 1992. Since then, Kazakhstan managed to hold the summit of the leaders of the CIS member states twice in 2002 and 2006. These meetings were highly appreciated internationally. On June 17, 2006, at the 2nd summit of the ICRC held in Almaty, a declaration was signed and an agreement was signed on the joint resolution of the main issues of cooperation and security in Asia by the participants of the forum. the secretariat of this organization. Currently, 20 Asian countries are members, 7 countries and 3 international organizations have observer status.

The work of this forum is aimed at strengthening stability and security in Asia, and this organization has become a platform for peaceful dialogue and solving complex geopolitical problems on the Asian continent. The 63rd session of the Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (UN ESCAOP) held in Almaty with the participation of more than 400 delegates from 62 ESCAAP countries was an important event for Kazakhstan and all of Central Asia. It is worth noting that the event of this level was held for the first time in Central Asia. Establishing relations with international and regional organizations is of particular importance in the developing international situation. Their main activity is related to security. It should be noted that the event of this level was held for the first time in Central Asia. Establishing relations with international and regional organizations is of particular importance in the developing international situation. Their main activity is related to security. It should be noted that the event of this level was held for the first time in Central Asia. Establishing relations with international and regional organizations is of particular importance in the developing international situation.

Their main activity is related to security. One of these organizations is the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). Since 2001, the Republic of Kazakhstan has participated in the initiative to establish the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), and its activities within this organization have become one of the main directions of foreign policy. Currently, the SCO includes Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, the People's Republic of China, Russia, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan, and Mongolia, Iran, India, and Pakistan are observer states in this organization. Thanks to the dialogue within the SCO, Kazakhstan had the opportunity to hold a constructive dialogue aimed at solving many problems in the political, trade-economic and humanitarian spheres, and within the framework of this organization, the issues of mobilization of forces in the fight against terrorism, extremism and separatism are discussed. . The SCO's important role in ensuring

political stability and security has made it an internationally influential organization.

Concept of foreign policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2030

On March 6, 2020, the concept of foreign policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2030 was announced. The document is based on the following priority directions: - open, predictable and consistent foreign policy of the country, which has a progressive character and will maintain its coherence with the continuation of the foreign policy direction of the First President - Elbashi in a new stage . development of the country; - protection of human rights, development of humanitarian diplomacy and environmental protection; - implementation of state policy on promotion of economic interests in the international arena, including investment attraction; - maintenance of international peace and security; - first of all, Russia, China, the USA, Central Asian countries and the countries of the European Union, and in terms of multilateral structures - the United Nations, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe are the main partners.

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